

NDAC/LO/015

1983 Jan 04

Third NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

1. Theory and Process Definitions

Process definitions for the Location Estimator (010), Star Mapper Preprocessing (011) and Attitude Reconstitution (014) have been delivered since the last report (008).

A new process, Star Mapper Stars Updating (SMSU) is proposed (014) in order to improve the star positions for the attitude reconstitution with shortest possible delay. SMSU would use residuals from the attitude reconstitution, which in turn would benefit greatly from the improved positions after only a few months.

Further tests of the IDT preprocessing algorithms (012) have confirmed the validity of data compression, but have also revealed some difficulties with the faintest stars which require further study. Also the effects of systematic reference phase errors (spin rate and acceleration errors) have been investigated in a preliminary way.

A study of attitude accuracy with dynamic and kinematic reconstitution (013) indicates (i) that dynamic modelling is probably not very effective; (ii) that the IC is almost accurate enough for the a posteriori attitude reconstitution; and (iii) that the attitude about z (ω or ψ) can probably be better than 0.1 as rms by inclusion of IDT data and using IC positions only.

2. Computer

A new minicomputer (HP9000) was ordered in November. By the autumn we plan to have a complete system with 1 Mb memory, 65 Mb Winchester disc with back-up, 1600 bpi tape deck, and FORTRAN 77 operating under HP-Unix. This upgrading is made possible by grants from the Wallenberg Foundation, the Swedish Board for Space Activities, and the Swedish Natural Science Research Council. The system will be used for the double-star algorithm development (WP8200) and later participation in TYCHO. It may also enable us to take part in the algorithm and programme development e.g. for the PRS Solution.

3. References

- NDAC/LO/009 Errata (2) WP3100: Preprocessing of IDT Data (Definition)
NDAC/LO/010 WP4100: Location Estimator (Definition)
NDAC/LO/011 WP1100: Preprocessing of SM Data (Definition)
NDAC/LO/012 Further Tests of the IDT Preprocessing Algorithms
NDAC/LO/013 Accuracy of Dynamic Versus Kinematic Attitude Reconstitution
NDAC/LO/014 WP2100: Attitude Reconstitution and SMS Update (Definition)
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- 1982 Oct 15 Step 3 solution of astrometric parameters and slit errors for single stars (Task Description)
1982 Nov 01 Sensitivity of astrometric parameters to systematic abscissa errors
1982 Nov 14 Star distribution models
1982 Nov 15 Phase errors of a trapezoidal slit profile
1982 Nov 22 TYCHO astrometry - error propagation